

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COMPLEX METALLIC FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES. PART IX.
CONDUCTOMETRIC AND THERMOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COPPER FERRICYANIDE

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The composition of copper ferricyanide by the conductometric and thermometric titrations of copper sulphate and potassium ferricyanide has been studied. The titrations have been carried out in the aqueous and aqueous-alcoholic medium. The composition arrived at approximates to $Cu_3(Fe^{III}Cy)_2$.

AnalR (B. D. H.) reagents were used for the preparation of the standard solutions of copper sulphate and potassium ferricyanide, which has been described in the previous communications (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 487 ; 1948, 25, 349). Conductometric and thermometric titration arrangements were similar to those used previously (*loc. cit.*). Using different concentrations of the two salt solutions, the titrations were carried out by the direct and reverse methods, *i. e.*, when copper sulphate from the burette was added to potassium ferricyanide taken in the conductivity cell or the Dewar's flask, and *vice versa*. The titrations were also carried out in presence of alcohol up to a total concentration of 20% by volume.

M/5.0 solution of copper sulphate would be referred as A/1-CuSO₄ soln. and M/10 solution of potassium ferricyanide as A/1-K₃FeCy₆ soln.

TABLE I

Direct conductometric titrations.

(i) A/1-CuSO₄ and A/10-K₃FeCy₆. Conc. ratio(n) = 10 : 1

A/10-K ₃ FeCy ₆ in the cell.	Alcohol added.	CuSO ₄ soln. reqd. for 'v' e.e. K ₃ FeCy ₆ in the cell.	CuSO ₄ soln. calc. for 10 e.e. A/10- K ₃ FeCy ₆ .	Equiv. vol. of A/10- CuSO ₄ .	Curve No.
(v)		(v ₁)	(v ₁ /v) x 10	n (v ₁ /v) x 10	
10 e.e.	0.0 e.e.	1.50 e.e.	1.50 e.e.	15.00 e.e.	1
9	1.0	1.34	1.49	14.88	2
8	2.0	1.18	1.475	14.75	3

TABLE I (Contd.)

Reverse conductometric titrations.(ii) A:2-K₃FeCy₆ and A/10-CuSO₄.

Conc. ratio(n) = 5 : 1.

A/10-CuSO ₄ in the cell. (v)	Alcohol added.	K ₃ FeCy ₆ reqd. for 'v' c.c. CuSO ₄ in the cell. (v ₁)	K ₃ FeCy ₆ calc. for 10 c.c. A/10-CuSO ₄ (v ₁ /v) × 10	Equiv. vol. of A/10- K ₃ FeCy ₆ n (v ₁ /v) × 10	Curve No.
10 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	1.29 c.c.	1.29 c.c.	6.45 c.c.	4
9.0	1.0	1.18	1.31	6.55	5
8.0	2.0	1.07	1.35	6.65	6

(iii) A 4-K₃FeCy₆ and A 10-CuSO₄.

Conc. ratio(n) = 2.5 : 1.

10 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	2.60 c.c.	2.60 c.c.	6.50 c.c.	7
9.0	1.0	2.38	2.64	6.61	8
8.0	2.0	2.12	2.65	6.62	9

TABLE II

Direct thermometric titrations.(i) A:2-CuSO₄ and A:10-K₃FeCy₆.

Conc. ratio(n) = 5 : 1.

A/10-K ₃ FeCy ₆ in the cell. (v)	Alcohol added.	CuSO ₄ reqd. for 'v' c.c. A/10-K ₃ FeCy ₆ in thermoflask. (v ₁)	CuSO ₄ calc. for 20 c.c. A/10-K ₃ FeCy ₆ (v ₁ /v) × 20	Equiv. vol. of A/10-CuSO ₄ . n (v ₁ /v) × 20	Curve No.
20 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	6.0 c.c.	6.00 c.c.	30.0 c.c.	10
18	2.0	5.35	5.94	29.72	11
16	4.0	4.65	5.81	29.05	12

(ii) A 4-CuSO₄ and A 10-K₃FeCy₆.

Conc. ratio(n) = 2.5 : 1.

20 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	11.95 c.c.	11.95 c.c.	29.9 c.c.	13
18	2.0	10.70	11.69	29.7	14
16	4.0	9.40	11.75	29.4	15

TABLE II (Contd.)

Reverse thermometric titrations

(i) A/10-K₃FeCy₆ and A/10-CuSO₄. Conc. ratio(n) = 2.5 : 1.

A/10-CuSO ₄ in thermos flask. (v)	Alcohol added.	K ₃ FeCy ₆ reqd. for 'v' c.c. CuSO ₄ in the thermos flask. (v ₁)	K ₃ FeCy ₆ calc. for 20 c.c. A/10-CuSO ₄ (v ₁ /v) × 20	Equiv. vol. of A/10- K ₃ FeCy ₆ n (v ₁ /v) × 20	Curve No.
20 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	5.20 c.c.	5.20 c.c.	13.00 c.c.	16
18	2.0	4.75	5.28	13.20	17
16	4.0	4.30	5.37	13.42	18

(ii) A/4-K₃FeCy₆ and A/4-CuSO₄. Conc. ratio(n) = 1 : 1.

20 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	13.0 c.c.	13.0 c.c.	13.0 c.c.	19
18	2.0	11.9	13.22	13.22	20
16	4.0	10.8	13.50	13.50	21

DISCUSSION

From the strengths of the solutions of copper sulphate (M/5.0) and potassium ferricyanide [M/5.1], the calculated titre values for the formation of the more probable compounds are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Formulae.	KCuFe ^{III} Cy ₆	Cu ₂ (Fe ^{III} Cy ₆) ₂
1. Titre value of CuSO ₄ for 10 c.c. of K ₃ FeCy ₆ soln. in the direct titrations ...	9.8 c.c.	14.70 c.c.
2. Titre value of K ₃ FeCy ₆ for 10 c.c. of CuSO ₄ soln. in the reverse titrations ...	10.2	6.8

Comparing these with the titre values obtained by the conductometric and thermometric titrations (Table I and II), it is obvious that both in the direct and reverse titrations the molecular composition of copper ferricyanide corresponds to Cu₂[Fe^{III}Cy₆]₂.

In the case of direct titrations (copper sulphate added to potassium ferricyanide), the observed titre values of copper sulphate (15.0 c.c.) in aqueous medium for 10 c.c. of potassium ferricyanide solution is higher than the calculated value (14.70 c.c.); while in the case of reverse titrations (K_3FeCys added to copper sulphate) the observed titre values of potassium ferricyanide (6.45 to 6.5 c.c.) for 10 c.c. of copper sulphate in aqueous medium are lower than the calculated value (6.80 c.c.) for

FIG. 1

the formation of the compound $Cu_2(Fe^{III}Cys)_2$. When the titrations are carried out in presence of increasing amounts of alcohol, the observed titre values both in the case of direct and reverse titrations approach the calculated titre values more closely.

FIG. 2

The discrepancy between the observed and the calculated titre values, (in direct and reverse titrations) in aqueous medium, and the subsequent change when the titrations are performed in aqueous-alcoholic medium, supports our view on hydrolytic and adsorptive nature of such complexes (cf. Parts I to VIII, this *Journal*).

On hydrolysis copper ferricyanide¹ would release some $FeCys^{III}$ which will consume some extra amount of copper sulphate, though a little it may be, hence the amount of copper sulphate required will be slightly greater than the calculated equivalent when

the titrations are carried out in aqueous medium by the direct process (copper sulphate added to potassium ferricyanide). And conversely in reverse titrations, a slight decrease in the titre value from the calculated equivalent will be observed when the titrations are performed in aqueous medium. In presence of alcohol the hydrolysis is checked to some extent, and thus the observed titre values both in the case of direct and reverse titrations approach the calculated ones more closely.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

The absorption of Cu and $FeCy_6^{III}$ ions by the precipitated copper ferricyanide may also bring about this discrepancy. In the case of direct titrations ($CuSO_4$ added to K_3FeCy_6) the precipitate is gradually formed in presence of $FeCy_6^{III}$ ions and the chances of absorption of these ions will be greater. In the case of reverse titrations (K_3FeCy_6 added to $CuSO_4$) on the other hand, the precipitate is formed in the medium of Cu^{II} , and hence it is likely that these ions will be absorbed more in this case. On this consideration the observed titre values both in the case of direct and reverse titrations would be lower than the calculated one for the formation of the probable

compound. This quite explains the lower observed value than the calculated one in the case of reverse titrations. But in the case of direct titrations the observed titre values of copper sulphate for 10 c.c. of potassium ferricyanide in aqueous medium are higher than the calculated one. This abnormality may be explained on the basis of the absorption experiments that have been carried out. Quantitative experiments have shown that copper ferricyanide sol absorbs Cu^{++} ions to a much greater extent than FeCy_6^{+++} ions. For the same value of equilibrium concentration (4.69 g./litre), the values of x/m for FeCy_6^{+++} and Cu^{++} ions have been found to be 0.14 and 0.70 m/moles respectively. Hence it appears that the sum total effect of the absorbed Cu^{++} and hydrolysis is greater than the loss of FeCy_6^{+++} due to its absorption by the precipitated complex in the cell. Hence the titre from the burette will be higher.

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

Thus the apparent discrepancy between the titre values as obtained by the thermometric and the conductometric methods, and those calculated on the basis of the strengths of the reacting solutions may be accounted for. In fact, it is difficult to account for the discrepancy by considering only one of these effects singly without considering the simultaneous effect of the other.

FIG. 7

FIG. 8

Quantitative absorption of Cu^{++} and $FeCy_6^{III}$ ions by copper ferricyanide sol, and the hydrolysis of the sol have been studied. The results will follow shortly.

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